

I-GUIDE Platform for Geospatial Data-Intensive Knowledge Discovery through Scalable Knowledge Graph and Object Storage

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The I-GUIDE Platform provides a scalable, user-centric online environment designed to support geospatial data-intensive convergence research and education. This science gateway enables knowledge discovery, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and computational reproducibility through integrated data infrastructure and AI tools.

The platform consists of three primary components: a React-based frontend, a Node.js backend, and a Neo4j graph database. All components are hosted on the Jetstream2 cloud infrastructure that is supported by the National Science Foundation. The platform supports dedicated **data hosting capabilities** through **MinIO**—a high-performance, S3-compatible object storage system—ensuring reliable storage of diverse research files, including large unstructured datasets and CyberGIS-Jupyter notebooks. Importantly, **DOI** can be issued for user-uploaded datasets, facilitating long-term discoverability and citation of data-intensive scientific knowledge.

Complementing spatially-aware discovery, **OpenSearch** is used for indexing and querying structured metadata and **GeoJSON-based spatial descriptors**. This enables the **Element Map** feature, which visualizes elements on an interactive map displaying their locations and boundaries. This allows users to intuitively explore spatial relationships between knowledge elements.

The platform's user interface provides seamless navigation, contribution, and collaboration capabilities, enabling users to access and manage spatially indexed content with ease. To further enhance user experience, the platform introduces a **smart search chatbot** powered by a **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** pipeline. The chatbot leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) and **spatial metadata** to provide context-aware, intelligent responses grounded in geospatial knowledge.

The platform also integrates a **JupyterHub environment**, enabling users to run uploaded notebooks using high-performance and cloud computing resources with pre-installed geospatial packages. Upcoming support for **GPU-enabled HPC resources** will further enhance performance for large-scale data analysis and modeling.

Platform stability is maintained through an **automated testing pipeline**, while an **administrative dashboard** facilitates content curation and user activity oversight, ensuring high-quality knowledge contributions and data integrity.

Users engage with the platform through a variety of use cases, including accessing categorized knowledge elements such as maps, datasets, Jupyter notebooks, publications, educational resources, and GitHub code repositories. The LLM-enabled smart search facilitates exploratory workflows by allowing natural language queries, thereby supporting intuitive access to relevant resources and results. To promote

discovery and contextual understanding, users can navigate related elements through the Element Map. Researchers can execute Jupyter notebooks directly within the platform via integrated JupyterHub support, enabling reproducible analysis. Additionally, the platform supports community-driven knowledge exchange, allowing users to contribute original or curated resources through submission forms and data upload interfaces, with the added option to generate DOIs for publishing datasets through the platform.

Together, these user-centric capabilities and core functionalities form a cohesive, extensible science gateway that empowers researchers and educators to share, explore, and analyze geospatial data for various convergence research and education purposes. By combining cloud-based storage, spatial metadata, AI-powered search, and computational tools at scale, the I-GUIDE Platform advances geospatial data-intensive convergence research, education, and innovation.

Keywords: cyberGIS, knowledge graph, convergence science, geospatial AI, science gateway

Portal URL: <https://platform.i-guide.io>

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Knowledge Element pages

This screenshot shows a detailed view of a knowledge element. It includes a title, author information (Alexander Christopher Wilbur), a summary of the research, a map of Illinois with highlighted areas, and a 'Related' section with a list of other relevant elements.

Element Map

I-GUIDE Platform

The homepage features a navigation menu with 'Knowledge Elements' highlighted. Below the menu are three main action buttons: 'Map' (Transform geospatial data into knowledge and insights), 'Connect' (Gain holistic understanding of linked knowledge elements), and 'Discover' (Seek new connections and knowledge through intelligent search). A search bar and a 'Start your exploration...' button are also visible.

Element Network

Homepage

The search results page for 'Chicago' displays a list of relevant knowledge elements. The top result is 'Chicago Communities: A geospatial dataset of communities within the city of Chicago.' Other results include 'Rapidly Measuring Spatial Accessibility of COVID-19 Healthcare Resources' and 'Mapping dynamic human sentiments of heat exposure with location-based social media data'. A 'Smart Search' bar at the bottom allows for further refinement.

Smart Search

Search

This screenshot shows a search results page for 'Chicago'. It lists 10 items, including datasets like 'Chicago Communities' and '1916 Chicago Map', and a notebook 'City-level Analysis at Chicago'. Each result includes a small thumbnail image and a brief description.

Acknowledgments: This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under award No. 2119329. Any opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

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